

Computer-Based Finite Element Analysis for Evaluating the Dynamic and Seismic Behaviour of Circular Footings

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Abstract: The response of circular footing to dynamic and seismic loading was a critical factor in foundation design. Due to symmetric design, the footing undergoes a combination of rotational, horizontal, and vertical moments when the footing subjected to dynamic loads. The interaction between the soil and the footing heavily impacts the behavior of the footing. The key factors such as soil stiffness, damping and nonlinear behavior are vital to overall response. Footing experience uneven settlement, tilting and rocking when it is subjected to seismic loads. The amplification of ground motion depends upon footing and soil properties. In this study the analysis is done to know the response of circular footing to dynamic and seismic loading conditions and to optimize the size of the footing. Finite element analysis is used analyze dynamic and seismic response of the footing.

Key Words: PLAXIS 2D, Dynamic Load, Seismic Load, Circular footing, Settlements.

1.INTRODUCTION

In recent years there is a rapid increase in civil engineering constructions, which results in projects on sites with challenging conditions. Because of excessive settlements, shallow foundations provide significant challenges while building on soft soil. Enhancing soft soil's bearing ability is therefore crucial. Traditionally, this is accomplished by adding strong granular soil to the existing soil up to the influence depth; however, this approach is frequently expensive and unworkable. Alternatively, it is usual practice to utilize a granular fill with horizontal layers of geosynthetic reinforcement. The composite behaviour of the granular fill and reinforcement in this geosynthetic-reinforced granular fill-soft soil system increases the soil's ability to carry loads. Geogrids made of polypropylene are frequently used as reinforcement. This strategy has been shown to be efficient in increasing the carrying capacity of shallow foundations on soft soil through numerous numerical studies and testing. (Milligan, 1987) (Maheshwari, 2012) (Chandan Ghosh, 1994) (S. Shukla, 1995) (Khing, 1993) (Yin,

1997) (K. Lee, 1999) (Sarvesh Chandra, 2005) (Kousik Deb, 2007) (Ahmet Demir M. L., 2013) (Ahmet Demir A. Y., 2013) . Several applications under static loading have effectively used ground improvement with various reinforcing materials (fibers, metal strips, or geosynthetics). It has been observed, therefore, that there is little research on the usage of fibers and geosynthetics as reinforcing materials with the soil beneath machine foundations. (Clement, 2015) (Samal, 2011) (Bhishm Singh Khati, 2012) (earth, 1991) Piles or shallow foundations may be used to support earthquake-prone structures. In contrast to the static scenario, the design of either type of foundation requires considerations because it must be safe for both the typical static loads and the dynamic loads imposed by earthquakes, machinery, metro trains, etc. The analogous static technique is frequently used to build shallow foundations in seismically active areas. (Vijay K. Puri, 2010).

2.OBJECTIVE

In this research an attempt was made to optimize footing size when it is subjected to dynamic load vertically and seismic load horizontally by creating models in PLAXIS 2D and analysing them by providing geogrid reinforcement for dynamic loading conditions and piles as reinforcement for seismic loading conditions

3.METHODOLOGY

Material Properties:

Table 1. Properties of footing used in the study.

Footing Material	Concrete
Young's modulus [Eref]	2.480E+07kN/m ²
Poisson ratio [v(nu)]	0.15
EA–Axial Stiffness (kN/m)	17.52E+0 ⁶
EI– Bending Stiffness (kN.m ² /m)	182 x10 ³

Table 2. Properties of cohesive soil used in the Study (Hussam Aldeen, 2022)

Property	Value
Specific gravity	2.65
Liquid Limit (%)	35
Plastic Limit (%)	20
Plasticity Index	15
Maximum dry unit weight(kN/m ²)	18.7
Optimum moisture content%	14.8
Cohesion(kN/m ²)	51

Table 3. Properties of Geosynthetic used in the Study (Ali Abdolhosseinzadeh, 2022)

Property	Value
Geogrid name	CE121
Aperture shape	Oval
Opening size (mm×mm)	6×8
Mesh thickness (mm)	3.3
Tensile strength (kN/m)	45
Axial stiffness (kN/m)	500
Mass per unit area (gr/m ²)	730

The behaviour of a circular foundation under various loading circumstances was examined using Finite Element Analysis (FEA) using PLAXIS 2D. The soil-structure interaction was modelled with suitable boundary conditions, and an axisymmetric model was used to faithfully depict the circular footing's shape. To adequately depict the underlying soil; soil parameters were allocated using data from boreholes. In addition to defining the footing's material and plate properties, the model also included the attributes of the geogrid reinforcement. To get baseline values for settlement under vertical dynamic loading and horizontal seismic loading, the model was first examined without reinforcement. A finer mesh was created around the footing and reinforcement to capture deformation. To evaluate its impact on lowering settlement, geogrid reinforcement of various lengths and spacings was added after the baseline was established. Seismic loading was then applied horizontally, although under seismic circumstances, geogrids had no discernible effect on settlement. Ultimately, piles were added to the model, and an analysis of the effect on settlement revealed a decrease in settlements, especially when seismic loading was present. The findings showed that piles were advantageous in lowering settlements in seismic situations, while geogrids were successful in lowering settlements under vertical dynamic loading but did not enhance performance under seismic loading.

Table4. Geometry Parameters used in the study for dynamic load

	Parameter	Value
Number of geogrid Layers	N	1,2,3,4,5
Length of geogrid	L	D,2D,3D,4D
Spacing from the footing to first geogrid	u	0.2D,0.4D
Spacing between geogrids	h	0.2D,0.4D,0.6D

Table5. Geometry Parameters used in the study for Seismic Load

	Parameter	Value
No of Piles used	P	2,4,6
Height of pile (m)	H	1,2,3
Spacing Between piles(m)	b	0.2,0.3,0.4,0.5
Placement of pile from the footing (m)	a	0.2,0.4

Table 6. Dynamic analysis parameters

Dynamic time	5 sec
Frequency	20 Hz
Amplitude	15°

Fig.no.1 Model of the 3.5m foundation generated in Praxis 2D

An axisymmetric model was created with a diameter of 3.5m, soil profile of 10m depth and 24m in lateral direction was considered for analysis. A dynamic load of 300kN was applied and analysis was done.

Fig.no.2 Deformed mesh model of 3.5m footing without reinforcement (Forced Vibration case)

Fig.no.3 Deformed mesh model of 3.5m footing without reinforcement (Free vibration case)

Figures numbers 2 and 3 represents forced vibration and free vibration models with a damping of 10%. The damping was applied to get the settlements in permissible limits (i.e 75mm). The settlements in both the cases were 72.86mm in forced vibration state and 71.23 in free vibration state.

Fig.no.4 Model of the foundation generated in Plaxis 2D

The footing was optimized to 2m with 350kN of dynamic load and 50kN of static load, with 5% damping by applying geo grid as reinforcement.

Fig.no.5 Deformed mesh model of 2m footing with reinforcement (Forced Vibration case)

Fig.no.6 Deformed mesh model of 2m footing with reinforcement (Free vibration case)

Fig no. 5 and 6 represents forced and free vibration of the footing of diameter 2m after application of reinforcement Settlements got reduced after applying geogrid reinforcement up to 0.6m from the footing. The footing size also got reduced after application of the reinforcement.

Fig.no.7 Deformed mesh model of 2m footing without pile reinforcement (Forced Vibration case)

Fig.no.8 Deformed mesh model of 2m footing without pile reinforcement (Free vibration case)

Figure numbers 7 and 8 represents forced and free vibration of the footing of diameter 2m. With a horizontal seismic load initially, the settlements are not with in the permissible limits.

Fig.no.9 Model of 1m foundation generated in Plaxis 2D

Fig no 9 represents the model developed in the software with 2m diameter in which piles are incorporated as reinforcement.

Fig.no.10 Deformed mesh model of 2m footing without pile reinforcement (Forced Vibration case)

Fig.no.11 Deformed mesh model of 2m footing with pile reinforcement (Free vibration case)

Figure numbers 10 and 11 represents forced and free vibration of the footing after applying piles as reinforcement, they are placed 0.2m from the footing after applying the pile reinforcement settlements are within the permissible limits.

4.RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Dynamic Loading: Initially the footing diameter was 3.5m with less than 75mm settlements, with 10% damping and without any soil improvement. Geogrid reinforcement is introduced to improve soil stability and to optimize the footing size.

Fig.no.8 Time Vs Deformation graph of 3.5 m footing with and without reinforcement with 10% damping.

The permissible settlements are obtained when the geogrid is placed in 3 layers of length 3 times the diameter ($L=3D$), spacing between the geo grid layers is $H=0.2D$ and spacing between footing and first geogrid layer and damping of 5%.

The study demonstrates that extending the geogrid's length (L) lowers settlement beneath a footing. However, when the geogrid length reaches $L = 3D$ the settlement reduction stabilizes. After this, settlement is not considerably decreased by extending the geogrid's length. And increasing spacing between geogrids the settlements will increase.

The application of 5% damping and reinforcement of geogrid resulted in a 22.31% reduction in settlement, or a 72.4 mm reduction. Geogrid and damping combine forces to promote soil stability and redistribute loads.

Because the reinforcement reduced excessive settlement, the footing was better able to withstand the applied load without experiencing considerable deformation, which indicates a significant increase in the stability of the foundation.

By retaining the foundation stable and functional under load conditions, the decreased settlement not only enhances the foundation's structural integrity but also improves its overall performance, averting further structural problems.

Optimization of footing:

Reduction footing diameter: There was a 42.8% reduction in the diameter of the footing, which was lowered by 2 meters.

Fig.no.12 Time Vs deformation graph for 2 m footing.

Impact of Reduction: By using damping and geogrid reinforcement, a more compact foundation design was made possible without compromising stability or structural integrity, as seen by this reduction in diameter.

Foundation Optimization: By reducing the footing size, the foundation system was optimized, improving design efficiency, and saving money and time. This size reduction demonstrates that reinforcement can allow for more efficient, economical, and compact designs without compromising performance.

Seismic Loading: There was no apparent impact of the geogrid on lowering settlements in case of seismic loading conditions.

Fig.no-18 Time Vs deformations graph

. The settlement dropped from 82 mm to 74.2 mm when six piles (spaced 0.2 m apart and 2 m deep) were utilized, indicating that the piles were more effective than the geogrid at reducing settlement. For extra safety, a 3-meter depth was selected even though a 2-meter depth would have been adequate. Better foundation stability is ensured by the deeper piles' access to more stable soil layers, which increase the safety margin against unanticipated settling problems

5. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to assess the properties of soil, improvement with geogrid and piles under circular footing. For dynamic loading the length of the geogrid, its number of layers, the spacing between each layer and spacing between the footing and first layer, and for seismic loading length of pile, spacing between the piles and spacing between footing and upper tip of pile and other factors are crucial for enhancing soil.

Dynamic Loading: There was a notable decrease in settlement when 5% damping and geogrid reinforcement ($L=3D$, $u=0.2D$, $H=0.2D$) were used. Without reinforcement, the settlement was 93.2 mm at initially. The settlement was decreased by 22.31% to 72.4 mm, however, when damping and geogrid were introduced. This decrease shows that the reinforcement was successful in increasing the foundation's stability, reducing excessive settlement, and enhancing overall performance.

The footing's diameter decreased by 1.5 meters, which is a 42.8% drop in size. This reduction in footing diameter indicates that a more compact foundation was made feasible while maintaining stability and structural integrity through the application of geogrid and damping reinforcement. The total foundation system was thus optimized by the smaller size, which also increased design efficiency and helped save both time and resources.

Seismic Loading: There was no apparent effect of the geogrid on lowering settlement. However, the settlement decreased from 82 mm to 74.2 mm when six piles were used (0.2 m spacing, 2 m depth). The 3-meter depth was selected for additional safety, even though a 2-meter pile depth would have been adequate. This is because it reaches more stable soil layers and offers a larger safety buffer against unanticipated settling problems.

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